

Smuggling of Migrants as an Influential Factor on National Security, Economic and Social Life

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Abstract—Human trafficking and smuggling of migrants are criminal activities, which are on the rise over recent years. The number of legal migrants arrived in Europe from outside the European Union are far less than those who want to come and settle in Europe. The objective of this paper is to present the impact on economic and social life of significant measures influencing the smuggling of migrants. The analysis is focused on various complex factors which have multiple origins and are highly influential as regard to the process of migration and the smuggling of migrants. The smuggling of migrants is a criminal activity, directly related to migration. The main results show that often the routes chosen for smuggling of migrants are circuitous, as smugglers carefully avoid strictly controlled roads, checkpoints, and countries or jurisdictions where there is efficiency of justice, with particular emphasis on the law on trafficking of persons and smuggling of migrants

Keywords—Corruption, migration, security, smuggling.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE human trafficking and smuggling of migrants has been an issue directly related to the right of freedom of movement. The term smuggling has been defined in different ways when it refers to movement across different States and especially in relation to migrants. The United Nations defines the smuggling of migrants as providing illegal entrance to a foreign country of a person, where this person has no citizenship or permanent residence, with the goal of providing direct or indirect financial or other material benefits. [1]

Salt and Stein have described the smuggling of migrants, as business model [2]. In this interpretation, they suggest the world migration to be looked at as global business, which has legitimate as well as illegitimate aspects. The business with migration has been studied as complex system of institutional networks, where income and costs are being recorded, individuals and firms, each of which seeks to derive commercial advantage or profit. This model takes the smuggling of migrants as an intermediate link in the business related to migration, to facilitate movement between the country of origin and country of destination the one in which the migrant wants to settle. The model has been divided into three stages: Mobilization and recruitment of migrants, their movements and their route towards the desired destination; their integration in their host countries and their realization in the labor market. When examining the pattern of smuggling of migrants as a business, the focus should not be at the migrants themselves, but to the efforts related to migration control with

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respect to the institutions involved, the smugglers and the interest in profit realization [3].

The desire of migrants to settle in Europe is motivated due to the improved economic outlook, the opportunities to find a good job, and the political and economic situation in the countries of origin. All these factors constitute a reason for the increased intensity in the smuggling of migrants activities. This issue has become a priority for EU Member States, particularly on topics related to border control and access regime within the EU. In 2010 in Europe there were over 140,000 victims of trafficking who have generated profit of over 3 billion USD for their exploiters [4].

II. IMPACT AND INFLUENCE OF SMUGGLING OF MIGRANTS ON ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL LIFE

Governments are taking actions to plan, regulate and control international migration, because this is directly related to the government ability to regulate the access to the national territory of foreign citizens and to prevent crossing of national borders and in cases of illegal entrance into the country.

The consequences of smuggling of migrants are generally expressed in reduced quality of governance in the country of origin, increasing corruption, violence against members of ethnic groups and increase of anti-migrant influence. Increased anti-migrant influence has created a specific impact on domestic politics, which increases the opportunities for integration of migrants after their identification.

Through activities related to smuggling of migrants, organized crime groups have recorded significant gains, thereby smuggling of migrants has become an integral part of economic life in the country.

In practice, migrant smuggling is related to violation of basic human rights, which forms a number of challenges to democratic societies. In recent years, a significant increase in the number of illegal migrants has been recorded in Europe. European countries are less inclined to regulate and legalize their status, in relation to the fact that such activity may be taken into account as rewarding illegal behavior of migrants, with connection to their illegal entry into European countries [5].

National security has been determined as activity related to protection and promotion of the well-being of citizens and legal residence of the territory of a country. The security itself is an important component of the national effort to control migration. The national control of migration could not be so effective if there is lack of co-operation between countries in relation to border security, law enforcement and establishment and operation of partner networks. The sharing of data

between competent authorities is crucial in relation to collection and analysis of information needed to prevent illegal migration activities. This should be achieved with respect to the existing differences in national privacy laws and with the enforcement of international strategies and mechanisms for dealing with security risks, as they are especially designed to meet such challenges.

International law facilitates migration-related security measures, as extradition rules and regulations related to extraterritorial enforcement of migration control are capable of guaranteeing security.

In order for the security threats to be limited, it is important to obtain a high level of pre-entry and entry control at national borders. It is crucial to prevent unauthorized movement of people, including cases when people migrate as part of a human smuggling scheme.

The link between illegal migration and smuggling of migrants is widely discussed in scientific literature and most authors agree that the smuggling of migrants plays a crucial role in facilitating illegal migration. The most common forms of illegal migration include illegal entry, exceeding the time permitted to stay in a foreign country or unauthorized employment. Smuggling of migrants plays a crucial role in facilitating illegal migration because smugglers offer and provide a wide range of services, starting from transportation, corrupting officials while crossing state borders, supplying people with false documents.

Illegal migration burdens considerably the social systems of a country in terms of accommodation, allowances, social payments, health insurance and social integration. In cases where institutions are not able to accept, accommodate and provide protection for the life and health of migrants and take steps for their integration, then the socio-economic crisis can quickly affect various other spheres of public life.

Illegal migration also has an impact on the labor market in a country. Most illegal migrants work without a necessary permission and under unregulated terms, without contracts, which has a negative effect on the social system. The hiring of illegal migrants does not comply with labor law, that way can work on extended working hours, lower payment and under harmful conditions, where at the same time no social security or health insurance payments have been made.

Humanities and social risks affect the criminal factor, which requires additional measures to address them, in order to minimize the possible short-term and long-term consequences [6].

III. THREATS FOR THE SECURITY

Significant number of migrants enters the European Union border every day, as most of them are irregular migrants. Migrants are using different routes to get to the European Union as commonly one way of entrance is through the Central Mediterranean and the other way is along the Western Mediterranean. When using the Western Mediterranean route of entering the European Union, migrants usually cross the border in Spain. This migration route is less significant in comparison with the routes via Bulgaria, Romania or Hungary.

It is significantly important for smugglers, as well as for migrants themselves to be constantly informed regarding any changes in crossing borders procedures, as well as amendments in legal regulations and procedures enforcement.

Knowledge comes from various sources, among which are family members and friends, while in some cases those are people who have travelled to the desired destination, as sometimes people have been forcibly removed from the destination country or in other cases they have voluntarily returned to the country of origin.

In relation to achieving the transfer to a certain destination in the process of migrant smuggling, it is not rare for migrants to have previously obtained information not only about their intended destination, but also the ways of contacting particular smugglers or even provide the name of a certain smuggler who can assure the transportation to the intended destination.

Smuggling of migrants is one of the fastest growing transnational criminal activities, including recruitment, transportation and arrival to the desired destination. There are three main differences between smuggling of migrants and trafficking of human beings, as they differ in three main aspects [7]:

- 1) Source of profit – When trafficking, the main source of profit is related to the primary objective – exploitation. Unlike the cases of human trafficking, in activities related to smuggling of migrants the profit is generated from activities of illegal crossing of borders and from the subsequent illegal residence. Once the migrant has crossed the border or has reached the desired destination, there is a reversed relationship between smugglers and migrants.
- 2) Transnationality – Migrant smuggling is always an international issue, involving at least two countries. The purpose of smuggling of migrants is always associated with the activities of illegal entry and stay in a country. In the case of human trafficking it is possible to exist an illegal entry and stay in the country, but this is not required. This means that human trafficking is not limited to persons who have no legal possibility to migrate. Moreover, human trafficking in most cases happens within the country of the origin of the victim, without crossing state borders;
- 3) Victimization – It is the process of converting individual, group of people or society in actual or potential victims of a separate offense or crime in general. Usually illegal migrants give their consent to the subject of smuggling. However, frequently there are cases where illegal migrants become victims of threats or violence. It is also possible, in the process of smuggling, migrants to withdraw their consent to give up on the smuggling scheme. Unlike cases of migrant smuggling, in human trafficking there is always a crime against one's personality. In the majority of cases, victims of trafficking never give their consent, or even if initially they consent, it negates the fact that traffickers use violence or fraud to gain control over them.

Human trafficking and smuggling of migrants vary and

despite the fact that illegal migrants have a contractual relationship with the smugglers, they remain free when they reach the desired destination, while victims of trafficking upon reaching the destination are enslaved and exploited by traffickers.

Human trafficking and especially migrant smuggling is strongly related to predisposition factors. Such factors include multicultural composition. Such composition mixes variety of cultures, customs and attitude towards enforcement of legislation. Sometimes prejudicial actions towards women and children are being observed, as well as towards minorities.

It is not known the extent to which smugglers gain profit from types of criminal activity apart from migrant smuggling, but in some activities a clear connection has been reported to constituting new multinational network.

The key asset to people offering activities related to smuggling of migrants, is connected to knowledge of specifics into migrant's everyday life as far as experience is concerned in relation to reaching the final destination of the route.

The main routes in smuggling illegal migrants to Europe coming from different parts of the world go through the Mediterranean Sea and across land borders in Eastern Europe, the Balkans and Turkey. Smuggling of migrants is complex in terms of logistics. Obstacles and difficulties related to entering the territory of the European Union involves a wide variety of intermediaries and organized crime groups at local, national and international level. Smugglers of migrants are well trained specialists, with logistics provided, who can manage transportation of migrants over long distances. They often have safe pensions, all along the transit routes for smuggling, as there they can hide their "cargo" in case of danger before they continue their contraband route. While not as sophisticated, strictly organized and scaled, as in cases of drug trafficking, trafficking of humans and smuggling of migrants require prior intelligence in order to successfully avoid obstacles and problems. The final destination for migrants is often the diaspora community where they can get integrated. [8]

IV. CRIMINAL GROUPS AS FACILITATING FACTOR IN MIGRANTS SMUGGLING

Introduction of restrictions associated with entrance of migrants into a country, creates a wide variety of organizers and accomplices in the process of smuggling migrants. This could be small groups or and international criminal organizations. Some of them only deal with migrant smuggling, while others are also involved in human trafficking. Often facilitators could not be considered as part of the criminal network. There may be cases in which inadvertently be aided smugglers of migrants. Often, owners of apartments or houses can rent them without knowing that they are used for pensions, where to stay illegal migrants. In other cases, employment agencies are often used as cover for smuggling and trafficking, which supports and facilitates the movement of migrants. In most cases employment agencies provide migrants by with low-skilled job positions and poorly paid work in the country of destination.

Several key persons are those who typically compose each criminal network, as one person is responsible for the coordination of all activities within the entire network. Usually persons who are announced to be leaders of the smuggling network are limiting their contacts to several core members of the network, which is due to the fact that leaders operate remotely.

Some leaders of smuggling networks are so called local leaders, while others are regional leaders, as in any case leaders are the ones who regulate the prices of activities within the network. Example of coordination activities includes order transfers, lorry drivers, document forgers, transporters, logisticians, etc.

Although the above discussed business model of migrant smuggling mainly refers to economic aspects, inevitably there is the need to consider the relationship between smuggling networks and organized crime groups.

According to article 2 of the United Nations Convention against transnational organized crime, organized criminal group is accepted that it is a structured group of three or more persons, existing for certain period of time, acting in regard with the aim of committing one or more serious offenses. The establishment of such group is in order to obtain directly or indirectly, a financial or other material benefit. [9] In many cases, however, the concept of organized crime is used in general, without reference to the definition given by the United Nations. It is the perception that organized criminal groups are different from other criminal groups that often specialize in a particular field of activity and have strictly regulated hierarchical structure often involve violent methods and corruption, as well as expand and legalize his economic activity [10].

As axiomatic could be determine the gender associated with human trafficking and smuggling of migrants and organized crime. It is widely believed that smuggling of migrants is an activity directly related to transnational, structured and controlled multi-million dollar organized crime network [11].

Smuggling of migrants could be defined as a security threat by detecting link between smuggling of migrants and criminal networks and terrorist organizations [12]. There are possible cases where part of the revenues from smuggling of migrants could be used for terrorist activities.

For some professional migrant smugglers it is important to have social contacts and good quality of life, because this provides them with guaranteed connections with officials and sometimes even with representatives of government institutions, including police authorities. There are cases where leaders of smuggling groups are well-respected members of local social community, who have been recognizable among the community members and have established good relations with representatives of competent local authorities. Other than that, there is also another type of migrant smugglers, who previously have been migrants themselves and who have knowledge on coordination activities, including details regarding travel conditions and details on where to buy false documents.

In certain cases, the illegal immigration is facilitated by

small organized groups, which do not have capability of planning and executing the overall trip from the country of origin to the destination country [13].

The contexts in which smugglers of migrants operate can significantly vary from one another. Illegality is usually associated with crossing a national border, in situation where migrants are in situation of need of services of person having the knowledge and resources required to circumvent the laws in force.

Different types of migrants have different sorts of experiences. On the basis of their experiences, some migrants develop a deep fear people form certain ethnic or race groups in society, for example.

Illegal migrants are increasingly looking to obtain false documents. Smuggling of migrants booming illegal business with false identity papers, visas, permits and other documents. Migrants seeking to obtain false documents / false birth certificates, fake residence permits for work or travel / thus can mislead the authorities, especially in cases in which they wish to obtain the status or other authorization guarantees their stay in the country. There may be cases in which illegal migrants are forced by smugglers to carry out criminal activities. Children or women can become victims of sexual exploitation or to carry out other illegal activities, or be subject to labor exploitation.

Some migrants are unable to find proper working conditions even in cases when they obtain a statute of migrants in a European Union country, just because they have been victims of migrant smuggling and have already experience the unfavorable conditions under which they are unable to find decent employment at the time when they experience lack of papers, frequently spurned by European societies.

Sometimes the expectations of migrants for better life over the European Union borders do not comply with the reality, where migrants are undergoing limitations, restrictions, discrimination and even isolation from domestic social groups in countries where they are trying to settle down and to start their normal life from the beginning.

V. CONCLUSION

Continuing migration pressure on European Union countries, combined with terrorist attacks in recent years is associated with growing concern that the routes of illegal migration may be used by radicalized foreign fighters or terrorist organizations.

International factors and structural changes have exerted a great impact on migration dynamics. External factors increased pressures on European borders, as the massive flow of migrants creates various concerns.

Identifying the links between illegal immigration and terrorism are mainly carried out in guidance related to the use of logistics channels of trafficking networks and smuggling in order to support terrorist activities. Although there is no concrete evidence to confirm that terrorist groups consistently rely and cooperate with organized criminal groups that smuggle of migrants reasonable assumption could be made that terrorist organizations use resources of trafficking

networks and smuggling to achieve their goals.

Coordination of security practices are able to facilitate the avoidance of risks and threats to the national security, economic systems and the social life. This could be managed in cases when security issues are solved through coordination paths and usage of national and international potentials of institutional governance.

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